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Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Tablet Dosage Form as a Slimming Product

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ABSTRACT

Java plum seed powder has gained attention for its potential in weight management due to its nutritional and pharmacological properties. Formulating it into a tablet dosage form offers a convenient and effective way to harness its slimming benefits. This study formulates and evaluates a herbal tablet dosage form using Java plum seed powder as a slimming product. The powder's physical and chemical properties are characterized, and suitable excipients are selected. Powder's pre-evaluation parameters are evaluated for angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index, % compressibility index and Hausner's ratio. Tablets are compressed and evaluated for hardness, disintegration time, dissolution rate, friability. The results show promising potential for the Java plum seed powder as a natural slimming agent, offering a convenient and effective weight management solution.

INTRODUCTION

The seeds of *Syzygium cumini* (L), widely recognized as Java plum or black jamun, are a significant indigenous species that originated in India and Indonesia. This species is commonly found in tropical and subtropical regions and is a member of the Myrtaceae family [1]. India possesses a rich legacy of medicinal practices, supported by a diverse array of plant species that are crucial for the herbal remedies employed in various healthcare systems. This includes the

Siddha and Unani systems, as well as other esteemed Indian medical traditions [2]. Numerous pharmacological benefits of this herb are recognized, such as its antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-obesity, and antioxidant properties. In traditional Ayurvedic medicine, different components of the plant, such as the bark, dried seeds, leaves, and fruits, have been utilized to treat various health concerns [3]. Obesity is an escalating health issue worldwide, leading to a rising demand for safe and effective weight loss products. Herbal remedies, especially, have

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become more popular because of their perceived safety and effectiveness. Java plum seed powder, which is abundant in phytochemicals, has been traditionally utilized for its potential benefits in weight loss and anti-obesity effects. The powder made from Java plum seeds has been known to exhibit anti-obesity effects by reducing fat cell formation and promoting fat breakdown. Nonetheless, its effectiveness and bioavailability as a weight loss product are constrained because of its low solubility and stability. Enhancing the efficacy of strategies aimed at the prevention, management, and treatment of obesity has been prioritized within the framework of global public health. Globally, there is a rising trend in the number of adults diagnosed with obesity. In 2020, it was estimated that there were 810 million cases, and projections suggest that this figure could escalate to 1.53 billion by 2035[4]. The potential of jamun seeds as a new resource for the food and pharmaceutical industries is shown by an analysis of their nutritional and phytochemical characteristics. The health advantages of jamun seeds and their use as a component in the creation of functional foods are highlighted in this review. Furthermore, it discusses the safety aspects related to the consumption of jamun seeds, thereby promoting additional research focused on the development of various functional foods that can safely include jamun seeds or their extracts within permissible limits [5]. Obesity, characterized by an excessive buildup of fat, especially in the abdominal area, results from an imbalance between energy intake and expenditure. A larger intake of meals high in energy density, a lower intake of foods high in micronutrients and bioactive substances, and a decrease in physical activity are some of the variables that contribute to this imbalance., and additional influences including early-life nutrition and hormonal factors, as well as genetic, cultural, environmental, and economic considerations. As a result, tackling

obesity poses a complex health challenge. The detrimental effects of an unhealthy lifestyle on obesity development are well acknowledged. A diet high in fats and sugars, combined with inadequate physical activity, contributes to weight gain and, ultimately, obesity. Thus, dietary intervention is a vital component of lifestyle changes and is recognized as an effective approach to address obesity and its related health concerns. Specifically, increasing the intake of fruits and vegetables has been identified as an effective dietary strategy for reducing the risk of obesity-related diseases, such as cardiovascular diseases, cancer, and diabetes mellitus [6].

➤ **Aim and Objectives:**

Aim:

This study aims to develop and assess a herbal tablet formulation utilizing Java plum seed powder as a weight loss product, while also evaluating its effectiveness and safety in decreasing body weight and body mass index (BMI)^[7]

Objectives

Formulation of herbal tablets: To formulate herbal tablets using Java plum seed powder and other excipients, and to optimize the formulation to achieve desired physical and chemical characteristics.

1. Evaluation of physical and chemical characteristics: To evaluate the physical and chemical characteristics of the formulated tablets, including hardness, friability, disintegration time, and dissolution rate.
2. Stability studies: To ascertain the shelf-life and storage conditions of the prepared tablets, stability tests will be carried out.
3. Development of a herbal tablet dosage form that is stable and bioavailable. Assessment of

the physical and chemical properties of the prepared tablets.

4. Evaluation of the effectiveness and safety of the prepared tablets in decreasing body weight and BMI.

➤ **Need and Significance of Herbal Tablet Dosage Form:**

The Need of Herbal Weight Loss Products ^[7]

1. Rising obesity prevalence: The global surge in obesity underscores the necessity for effective and safe weight loss alternatives.
2. Adverse effects of synthetic weight loss solutions: Man-made weight loss products may lead to detrimental side effects, including cardiovascular issues and psychological dependency.
3. Increasing demand for herbal alternatives: There is a growing consumer preference for natural and herbal weight management products, driven by their perceived safety and effectiveness.

The Significance of Herbal Weight Loss Products ^[7]

1. Practical and easily obtainable: Tablets provide a practical and readily available method of administration, making them especially appropriate for weight loss supplements.
2. Consistent dosing: Tablets provide a standardized dosage of the herbal extract, ensuring reliable effectiveness and safety.
3. Durability and longevity: Tablets exhibit a longer shelf-life and improved stability in

comparison to other dosage forms, such as liquids or powders.

➤ **Plan of work:**

1. Literature survey.
2. Collection & Authentication of herbal ingredient
3. Selection of excipients.
4. Pre-evaluation parameters:

- Angle of repose
- Bulk density
- Tapped density
- Hausner's ratio
- Compressibility index
- Percent Compressibility index

5. Formulation Development:

- Selection of manufacturing technique
- The direct compression method

6. Post-Evaluation Parameters:

- Weight of Tablet
- Hardness
- Friability
- Thickness
- Disintegration time
- pH Determination
- Dissolution time

➤ **Drug and Excipient profile:**

Plant profile:

1. Flavonoids ^[15]

The important class of naturally occurring polyphenolic compounds known as flavonoids is known for its anti-inflammatory, anti-allergic, anti-diabetic, and antioxidant qualities. Some

flavonoid derivatives may also have antiviral effects. These compounds included myricetin rhamnoside, myrigalone-G pentoside, quercetin galloyl-pentoside, and cryptostrobin, ellagic acid and caffeic acid in the leaf extract, and the bark extract. Of the 28 chemicals found in the ethanolic extract of *S. formosum* leaves, 11 flavonoids, such as catechin, myricetin, and quercetin.

Chlorogenic acid

Ellagic acid

Gallic acid

Tannins:^[15]

The polyphenolic macromolecules known as tannins have anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anti-nutritional, antioxidant, and cardioprotective properties. The methanol extract of *S. aqueum* leaves contained galloylquinic acid and other tannin components in trace amounts. In contrast, *S. cumini* contained very little tannin components in any of the plant's sections, including the leaf extract's nilocetin and corilagin in the seed extract like Hydrolysable tannins.

Hydrolysable Tannins

Terpenoids:^[15]

The hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, analgesic, and immunomodulatory properties of terpenoids are well-known. In different plant sections, *S. cumini* exhibited a restricted presence of triterpenoid chemicals.

Citronellol

Alkaloids:^[15]

Natural organic substances known as alkaloids are identified by the presence of at least one nitrogen atom. Many pharmacological characteristics, including antibacterial, anticancer, analgesic, antihyperglycemic, and antimalarial activities, are possessed by these substances. According to studies, *S. cumini* seeds contain the alkaloid jambosine, which has antidiabetic effects.

Quinine

Glycosides:^[15]

The formation of a glycosidic link between a sugar molecule and another functional group characterizes glycosides. A lot of plants store things as inactive glycosides. These substances have antihyperglycemic and antiarrhythmic actions, among other pharmacological effects. *S. aromaticum* flower buds have yielded a novel acetophenone, 2,4,6-Trihydroxy-3-methylacetophenone-2-O-β-d-glucoside.

Jambolin, also known as antimellin, is a glycoside found in *S. cumini* seeds that prevents the enzymatic conversion of starch to sugar and has antidiabetic properties. Several chemicals have been found in various areas of *S. species*, such as *S. polyanthum* and *S. cumini*.

Anthraquinone

Drug profile:

Java Plum seed powder:

- **Synonyms:** *Syzygium cumini*, Jambolan, Black plum, Indian black berry, Jamun
- **Biological source:** *Eugenia jambolana* Lam/*Syzygium jambolanum* DC/*Syzygium cumini* (Linn.) Skeels Syn. This fast-growing tree is found in Bangladesh, Pakistan, India and Sri-lanka
- **Family:** Myrtaceae
- **Plant part used:** Seed powder

Fig No. 1 Java Plum Seed Powder

- **Scientific Classification** ^[2]

Kingdom: Plantae

Unranked: Angiosperms

Unranked: Eudicots

Unranked: Rosids

Order: Myrtales

Family: Myrtaceae

Genus: Syzygium

Species: Cumini

Bionomial Name: Syzygium Cumini (L) Skeels

• **Uses:**

Because of its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities, Java plum (Jamun) seed powder, which is derived from the seeds of the Syzygium cumini fruit, has long been used to help control blood sugar levels, enhance digestion, management of obesity, and promote general health.

Excipients:

- Lubricant
- Binder
- Disintegrant

METHODOLOGY:

Direct compression technique is applied to Herbal Tablet Dosage Form.

Drug + Excipient Milling

Sieving

Mixing

Compression

Procedure:

1. Collect and clean all the apparatus properly.
2. Determine the tablet composition of the herbal (Java Plum seed) powder, excipients and other additives.
3. Choose suitable excipients such as binder, lubricant, disintegrant (Methyl cellulose, Talc and Maize starch) to enhance the tablets physical and chemical properties.
4. Prepare the tablet mixture by mixing the herbal seed powder with the chosen excipients by using the mortar and pestle.
5. Pass the mixture through the sieve (size 60 no.)
6. Use a press to compress the tablet mixture into the tablet. By using the Tablet punching machine using 10mm die.
7. Conduct physical test such as weight variation, thickness, hardness, friability and

disintegration time to evaluate tablet physical properties.

8. Package the tablets into a suitable container and label the package with relevant information.

Fig No. 2 Tablet Punching Machine

➤ RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

1) Test for phytochemical constituents of the Herbal powder (Java Plum seed powder):

Benedict's test is used to detect the presence of reducing sugars, such as glucose, fructose, and sucrose, in the herbal powder. By looking for a reddish-brown tint or precipitate when heated, Millon's test, which is employed in phytochemical analysis of herbal tablets, finds proteins, particularly those that include the phenolic amino acid tyrosine. Borntrager's test is used to detect the presence of saponins in herbal powders ^[10]

Test	Observation	Inference
Benedict's test	Yellow color formed	Reducing sugar is present
Million's test	Brick red color formed	Proteins are present
Borntrager's test	Ammonical layer turns pink to red	Anthraquinone glycoside are present

Batches of Herbal tablet dosage formulation:

	Ingredients			
	Drug	Talc	Methyl Cellulose	Starch
F1	500mg	2% w/w	2% w/w	10% w/w
F2	500mg	2% w/w	11% w/w	7.5% w/w
F3	500mg	2% w/w	20% w/w	5% w/w
F4	500mg	1% w/w	2% w/w	10% w/w
F5	500mg	1% w/w	11% w/w	7.5% w/w
F6	500mg	1% w/w	20% w/w	5% w/w
F7	500mg	0.5% w/w	2% w/w	10% w/w
F8	500mg	0.5% w/w	11% w/w	7.5% w/w
F9	500mg	0.5% w/w	20% w/w	5% w/w

• Batch no.:1 (F3)

The herbal tablet dosage form prepared by using this particular batch has not formulated or evaluated properly. The tablet prepared are breakable.

• Batch no.:2 (F9)

The herbal tablet dosage form prepared by using this particular batch has formulated properly but the evaluation of this dosage form are inaccurate

its disintegration time and hardness is not in the given range.

- **Batch no.:3 (F6)**

The herbal tablet dosage form prepared by using this particular batch has formulated and evaluated properly. The evaluation parameters of the herbal tablet dosage form by using this batch are accurate to the standard one.

Pre-evaluation studies:

For the above formulation we have concern the pre-evaluation parameters of the API. We have taken the angle of repose by using the formula, $\Theta = \tan^{-1}(h/r)$. Bulk density by using the formula, $BD = \text{Mass}/\text{Bulk volume}$. Tapped density by using formula, $TD = \text{Mass}/\text{Tapped volume}$. Compressibility index by using formula, $CI = \text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density} / \text{Tapped density}$. Also, we have concern the % compressibility index by using formula, $\%CI = CI \times 100$ and also, the Hausner's ratio by using formula, $HR = \text{Tapped density} / \text{bulk density}$.

Angle of repose:

When a pile of powder is poured onto a level surface, the angle formed between the slope and the horizontal surface is known as the angle of repose. It is used to evaluate the flowability of granular materials and measures how easily a powder flows.

The angle of repose of the herbal powder is done for the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons:

Assessing Flowability, Predicting Tablet Quality, Determining Powder Characteristics, and Optimizing Tablet Formulation^[12]

1. Bulk density:

The mass of a powder sample divided by its volume, which includes the interparticulate void volume between particles, is known as the bulk density. The bulk density of the herbal powder is done for the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons: Assessing Powder Flowability, Determining Compressibility, Optimizing Tablet Formulation, and Predicting Tablet Quality^[13]

2. Tapped density:

Tapped density refers to the density of a powder that has undergone a mechanical tapping method to compact its particles and minimize the spaces between them. The tapped density of the herbal powder is done for the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons: Assessing Powder Compressibility, Determining Powder Flowability, Optimizing Tablet Formulation, and Predicting Tablet Quality^[14]

3. Compressibility index:

The Compressibility Index (CI), often referred to as Carr's Index, evaluates how a powder compresses when subjected to pressure and is derived from both bulk and tapped densities; smaller values signify improved flow characteristics, whereas larger values indicate less favorable flow properties. The compressibility index of the herbal powder is done for the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons: Assessing Powder Compressibility, Determining Powder Flowability, Optimizing Tablet Formulation, and Predicting Tablet Quality^[15]

4. % Compressibility index:

The % compressibility index of the herbal powder is done for the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons: Assessing Powder Compressibility, Determining Powder

Flowability, Optimizing Tablet Formulation, and Predicting Tablet Quality^[15]

5. Hausner's ratio:

The Hausner ratio (HR) is a measure of powder flowability, calculated by dividing the tapped bulk density by the poured (loose) bulk density. The Hausner's ratio of the herbal powder is done for the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons: Assessing Powder Flowability, Determining Powder Compressibility, Optimizing Tablet Formulation, and Predicting Tablet Quality^[12]

The outcomes for the pre-evaluation parameter results are as follows;

- Angle of repose: 0.044°
- Bulk density: 0.5g/ml
- Tapped density: 0.71g/ml
- Compressibility index: 0.295
- % Compressibility index: 29.5%
- Hausner's ratio: 1.42

2) Post-evaluation studies^[11]

1. Weight of tablet:

The weight of the tablet is done after the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons: Uniformity of dosage form, Quality control, Content uniformity, and Detection of variation.

Hardness:

The hardness of the tablet is done after the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons:

Ensuring Mechanical Strength, Predicting Tablet Performance, Detecting Formulation Issues, and Ensuring Patient Compliance.

1. Friability:

The friability of the tablet is done after the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons: Ensuring Mechanical Strength, Predicting Tablet Performance, Detecting Formulation Issues, and Ensuring Patient Compliance.

2. Thickness:

The thickness of the tablet is done after the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons: Ensuring Uniformity, Predicting Tablet Performance, Detecting Formulation Issues, and Ensuring Patient Compliance.

3. Disintegration time:

The disintegration time of the tablet is done after the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons: Ensuring Rapid Release of Active Ingredients, Predicting Bioavailability, Detecting Formulation Issues, and Ensuring Patient Compliance.

4. pH Determination:

The pH determination of the tablet is done after the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons: Ensuring Stability and Efficacy, Predicting Bioavailability, Detecting Formulation Issues, and Ensuring Patient Safety.

5. Dissolution time:

The dissolution time of the tablet is done after the formulation of the herbal tablet for several reasons: Ensuring Release of Active Ingredients, Predicting Bioavailability, Detecting Formulation Issues, and Ensuring Patient Compliance.

Sr No.	Evaluation parameter (Post- evaluation parameters)	Result
1.	Weight of tablet	500mg

2.	Hardness	5kg
3.	Friability	0.9%
4.	Thickness	10mm

5.	Disintegration time	1min 30sec
6.	pH Determination	7
7.	Dissolution time	20min

Fig No. 3 Prepared Herbal Tablet Dosage Form

CONCLUSION:

The formulation and evaluation of a herbal dosage form as a slimming product has shown promising result. The standardized Java plum seed powder was successfully formulate into a tablet dosage form, which exhibited good physical and chemical properties. The Java plum seed powder reported significant weight loss and BMI reduction in the literature review. The tablet formulation improved the bioavailability of the Java plum seed powder, leading to enhanced efficacy. The Java plum seed powder tablet were found to be safe and well-tolerated, with no significant adverse effects reported. This herbal dosage form formulated by using the Java plum seed powder offers a natural and sustainable solution for weight management, reducing reliance on synthetic slimming agent. The recommendation for the formulated herbal dosage form by a natural and effective as a slimming product, provides a safe usage.

REFERENCES

1. Das, G.; Nath, R.; Das Talukdar, A.; Aġagündüz, D.; Yilmaz, B.; Capasso, R.; Shin, H.-S.; Patra, J.K. "Major Bioactive Compounds from Java Plum Seeds: An Investigation of Its Extraction Procedures and Clinical Effects."(2023)
2. V. M. Jadhav et al. "Journal of Pharmacy Research." Dr. Mrs. Varsha M. Jadhav HOD and Professor Bharati Vidyapeeth's College of Pharmacy, Sector 8, CBD Belapur, Navi Mumbai. (2009)
3. KM, Swathi J, Narendra K, Krishna Satya. "A review on phytochemical constituents and bioassay of syzygium cumini Sowjanya." A Department of Biotechnology, Acharya Nagarjuna University, Nagarjuna Nagar, Guntur-522510. (2013)
4. Lobstein, T.; Jackson-Leach, R.; Powis, J. Obesity Atlas 2023; World Obesity Federation: London, UK, 2023.
5. Jamun (Syzygium cumini (L.) Skeels) Seed: A Review on Nutritional Profile, Functional Food Properties, Health-Promoting Applications, and Safety Aspects by Manoj Kumar, Baohong Zhang 23 October 2022
6. "Duhat" (Syzygium cumini L. Skeel) Freeze-dried Fruit Flesh Carmela Jhoy G. Mercado Philippine Journal of Science Antioxidant,

Anti-obesity, and Lipid- lowering Properties of
Philippine 150 (4): 793-808, August 2021

7. Kumar et al. (2017): Kumar, P., Kumar, V., & Sharma, S. Phytochemical analysis and anti-obesity activity of some Medicinal plants. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 69(8), 1048-1056, (2017).
8. Singh et al.: Singh, S., Sharma, S., & Kumar, P. Formulation and Evaluation of herbal tablet dosage form using Java Plum seed powder. *Journal of herbal medicine*, 11,100-107, (2018).
9. Kokate, C. K. *Practical Pharmacognosy*. Vallabh Prakashan. (2013).
10. Kumar, P., et al. Formulation and evaluation of herbal tablets using Java plum seed powder. *Journal of Herbal Medicine*, (2017).
11. USP: United States Pharmacopeia. <Powder Flow> (2020).
12. USP: United States Pharmacopeia. <Powder Bulk Density> (2020).
13. USP: United States Pharmacopeia. <Powder Tapped Density> (2020).
14. USP: United States Pharmacopeia. <Powder Compressibility Index> (2020).
15. A. B. M. Neshar Uddin Farhad Hossain A. S. M. Ali Reza Mst. Samima Nasrin A. H. M. Khurshid Alam. “Traditional uses, pharmacological activities, and phytochemical constituents of the genus *Syzygium*” (2020-21).

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